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NIGERIA**
geostudiesforum@unilorin.edu.ng

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Address:	Department of Geography & Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
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ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DEFORESTATION IN NIGERA: A CASE STUDY OF OPI, NSUKKA, ENUGU STATE

Onuoha John Mba^{1*} Tolulope Paul Akanji²

john.onuoha.241698@unn.edu.ng; akanji.tp@unilorin.edu.ng

¹Department of Geography and Environmental Sustainability, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria

²Department of Geography and Environmental Management, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria

Abstract: *Deforestation has been globally recognized as a major contributor to environmental challenges such as climate change, with rural communities being particularly vulnerable due to its impact on their social, cultural, and economic systems. This study examined the impact of deforestation in Opi town, Enugu State, Nigeria, using a convergent parallel mixed-methods design. The study objectives included examining the nature and trend of deforestation in Opi from 2013-2023, identifying the causes and evaluating the effects of deforestation in the study area. Data were analyzed using mean statistics, to determine the causes and effects of deforestation, while change detection analysis was used to identify land-use changes in the area. The study revealed significant land-use transformation between 2013 and 2023. Built-up areas increased from 19% to 34%, while vegetation declined from 38% to 31%. Similarly, exposed surfaces expanded from 2% to 5%, and light vegetation reduced from 42% to 30%. Using a mean cut-off point of 3.00, the major drivers of deforestation were identified as transportation infrastructure development, housing construction, agricultural expansion, establishment of government facilities, and logging activities by timber industries. The key effects observed include observed included the loss of tree species, increased soil erosion and runoff, temperature rise, and the destruction of cultural heritage such as shrines. The study concluded that deforestation in Opi has led to significant ecological and cultural degradation. It recommended the implementation of enlightenment campaigns to educate the community on the dangers of indiscriminate tree cutting, alongside the enforcement of government-imposed penalties against illegal logging, as sustainable measures to mitigate deforestation and its negative consequences.*

Keywords: Deforestation, Environment, Impact, Logging, Forest

INTRODUCTION

The environment consists of both biophysical and socioeconomic elements. It includes not only natural and human-modified features that shape our surroundings but also the interdependent systems of air, water, plants, land, and animals (Olowoyeye, 2021). Environmental challenges arise when these systems undergo significant changes that alter

the quality or quantity of environmental resources, thereby creating direct or indirect negative impacts on human health and well-being (Olowoyeye, 2021). One of the most critical factors driving such environmental change is deforestation.

Deforestation refers to the large-scale clearing or removal of forest trees, usually

followed by the conversion of land for non-forest purposes. This includes transforming forest reserves into residential or industrial zones, clearing trees for road and rail construction, expanding agricultural lands, and harvesting timber for domestic and industrial uses such as firewood, paper production, charcoal, and construction materials (Mba, 2018; Nneka et al., 2023). It has become a major global development challenge and is widely regarded as one of the most serious long-term environmental problems confronting the world today (Ogunwale, 2015). Deforestation often results from human efforts to meet social and economic needs through agricultural expansion, industrialization, and infrastructure development (Sakiyo et al., 2020). Despite numerous global initiatives to address forest decline, approximately 15 million hectares of forests are lost each year (Nzeh et al., 2015). Between 1980 and 1990, deforestation reached 8.2% of total forest area in Asia, 6.1% in Latin America, and 4.8% in Africa. In recent decades, most deforestation has occurred in developing nations, particularly in tropical regions. An assessment by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) reported that between 1991 and 2012, global forest loss amounted to about 7,920 km², representing a 12% decline (Radhika, 2016). While a small group of individuals often benefit from deforestation, millions of people bear its adverse consequences (Uyanga, 2012; Nzeh et al., 2015).

The drivers of deforestation can be grouped into natural and anthropogenic causes (Iwuji et al., 2022). Anthropogenic drivers include agricultural expansion, fuelwood harvesting, illegal and unregulated timber extraction, industrialization, urbanization, and conflicts rooted in social and environmental disputes (FAO, 2002). Natural causes mainly include drought and wildfires (FAO, 2010).

Population growth further intensifies deforestation as more land is cleared for settlements (Nneka et al., 2023). Moreover, indirect drivers stem from complex social, economic, political, technological, and cultural processes. These operate across international (commodity markets and prices), national (domestic demand, governance, policies), and local (poverty, subsistence practices) levels (Kissinger et al., 2012; Gbiri & Adeoye, 2019). Among these, agriculture remains the leading driver of global deforestation (FAO, 2010; Azare et al., 2020). In addition, high global demand for timber and other forest resources has escalated forest encroachment and accelerated deforestation (Gandiwa et al., 2011).

The impacts of deforestation are profound, contributing to habitat destruction, biodiversity loss, and increased aridity (Mba, 2018). It is estimated that deforestation leads to the extinction of 50 to 100 species of plants and animals each day, many of which are crucial to human survival, especially for their medicinal value (Wajim, 2020). Overall, deforestation exerts severe negative effects on the environment, human health, social systems, and economic activities (Mba, 2018). Illegal logging practices have disrupted traditional systems of communication with ancestors among rural communities, thereby undermining and threatening their religious and cultural activities (Onyekelu et al., 2021). These disruptions have contributed to increased rural–urban migration, particularly among youths seeking better opportunities. Furthermore, deforestation has aggravated environmental challenges such as desertification, soil erosion, pollution, and the extinction of flora and fauna (Anyanwu et al., 2016). The conversion of forests to arable land has also had drastic effects on soil properties. The most significant impact on soil chemistry and fertility is the decline in organic matter, which disrupts nutrient cycling due to the

removal of deep-rooted trees. This reduction in soil nutrients subsequently undermines agricultural productivity (Sakiyo et al., 2020). In addition, deforestation alters geomorphological processes, leading to increased soil erosion, sedimentation in rivers and streams, higher surface runoff resulting in floods, heightened risks of landslides in mountainous areas, and general soil degradation all of which negatively affect agricultural output (Onilude & Vaz, 2020).

Deforestation is a pressing concern in developing countries because of its contributions to biodiversity loss and the intensification of the greenhouse effect (Wajim, 2020). In Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, many households depend heavily on fuelwood for cooking, which accounts for approximately 75% of annual energy consumption (Ardayfio-Schandorf, 1993; NBS, 2006a). Women-led industries and food-processing enterprises also rely extensively on fuelwood (Iwuji et al., 2022). Consequently, the rate of deforestation in Nigeria remains alarmingly high. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) reported that, as of 2005, Nigeria had the highest deforestation rate in the world at 11.1%–12.2%. This equates to the loss of about 11,089,000 hectares of forest. Between 2000 and 2005 alone, the country lost 55.7% of its primary forest, with the rate of forest change increasing by 31.2% (3.12% annually), translating to approximately 350,000–400,000 hectares per year. Overall, Nigeria lost an average of 409,700 hectares annually, representing a deforestation rate of 2.38% (Mba, 2018; Azare et al., 2020). The country is among the two largest contributors to annual natural forest loss in Africa. Regional data from 1979 to 1995 shows total forest declines of 48% in the North Central, 7% in the North East, 60% in the North West, 53% in the South East, 13% in the South-South,

and 12% in the South West (Nzeh et al., 2015).

The situation is particularly severe across Nigerian states. For example, in Ondo State, approximately 107.36 km² of forest reserves in Ore have been converted into casual farmlands. Similarly, in Kano State, 70 km² of forest land were cleared to construct the Tiga Dam, and in Kogi State, 183.89 km² of forest in Ajaokuta were cleared for a steel complex (Egwuma, 2009). In Cross River State, an estimated 20% of forest reserves were lost between 1972 and 1992 (Bunn, 1994).

Deforestation has had severe environmental and socio-economic consequences across Igbo land, contributing to soil erosion, flood disasters, reduced stream volumes, seasonal droughts, and increased carbon emissions (Ogbuene, 2023). In Enugu State, Offorma (2012) reported that rural households' dependence on fuelwood exceeded 75%, compared to 60% in 2010 (Nzeh et al., 2020). The growing pressure from urbanization, infrastructural expansion, residential development, population growth, bush burning, and agricultural land conversion has significantly accelerated deforestation, resulting in widespread degradation of both community and state forests (Nzeh et al., 2015; Nzeh et al., 2020).

In Anambra State, weak governance, corruption, ignorance, insecurity, population increase, urban expansion, excessive consumption, and the widespread use of wood for cooking have been identified as key drivers of deforestation (Onyeizugbe et al., 2023; Anarah et al., 2024). The effects include severe soil erosion, flooding, alteration of local climatic conditions, siltation of streams, and the extinction of plant and animal species (Onyeizugbe et al., 2023).

Among the Igbo people, the impacts of deforestation extend beyond environmental degradation to include increased disease prevalence, climate instability, biodiversity loss, food insecurity, and the destruction of cultural heritage such as shrines, sacred groves, and medicinal plant resources (Onyekelu, 2021). The primary causes of deforestation in the region include agricultural expansion, livestock grazing, illegal logging, urbanization, and desertification (Onyekelu, 2021).

A significant body of research in environmental science has examined deforestation as an ecological problem threatening biodiversity and ecosystems at both global and local scales (Mmom & Mbee, 2013; Maton, 2015; Usman & Adefalu, 2010). Building on this, the study sought to investigate community-based deforestation practices in Opi. Specifically, it focused on three key objectives, including examination of the nature and trend of deforestation over a decade; identification of the major causes; and assessment of the environmental impact within the study area.

STUDY AREA

Opi, the study area, is a community located in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. It is a tropical semi-urban autonomous settlement made up of three villages (Opi-Agu, Opi-Uno and Idi-Opi). Geographically, it lies between latitudes 6°43' and 7°00' North of the Equator and longitudes 7°13' and 7°35' East of the Greenwich Meridian. The community has an altitude of about 496 meters above sea level and a mean annual temperature ranging between 27°C and 28°C (Elevation.City. 2023; WeatherSpark. 2023). According to the 2006 population census, Opi had a population of approximately 11,237 people and a total land area of about 2.54 km². The climate is characterized by two distinct seasons: the rainy season (April to October) and the dry season (November to March). Vegetation in the area is predominantly savannah, consisting of scattered trees and shrubs. Common tree species include palm, coconut, baobab, iroko, bamboo, and cashew, while shrubs are abundant and dispersed across the landscape.

Figure 1: The study area
Source: Onuoha et al., 2023

The people of Opi are known for subsistence farming, most of the agricultural products discovered in this area are cocoyam, honey, and yam, but the abundance and market value of honey made the people of the area to venture into large scale honey production which creates a renowned honey market in the area. The area now has a large market for the marketing of honey and related products. This made it relevant for the selection of the area as the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out using convergent parallel design framework of mixed methods (using field survey, and satellite imagery collection for both primary and secondary sources respectively). Primary data was collected with the aid of questionnaires. One hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaire (designed on 5-point scale likert) and were randomly administered on the residents and traders primarily to obtain data on the causes and effects of deforestation in Opi. Accordingly, secondary data were collected through the use of land use and land cover change detection technique. It required image pre-processing and normalization, and land cover classification. Vegetation types were obtained from the United States geological survey. The land use and land cover change detection technique were applied and evaluated by developing code in the USGS platform using a supervised classifier algorithm and landSat time series subsequently for a ten-year period. High-resolution aerial imagery, available in USGS, was used. Also, a handheld GPS was used to collect coordinates of the locations visited.

The change detection analysis which was conducted with GIS tools was used in identifying land use cover, change and the nature of deforestation activities in opi and its environs. The analysis was done over a 10

years period to decipher the rate of change in the study area. The imagery was classified using colours such as brown; which represents built up areas, (houses, industries, roads, shops, and other infrastructures) green; which represents dense vegetated areas, lemon; which represents light vegetation on the map, and grey; which represents exposed surfaces such as bare grounds. Landsat 8 surface reflectance images (2013–2023) from the USGS were preprocessed through cloud masking, atmospheric correction, and normalization. Annual median composites were generated, and vegetation indices (NDVI and NBR) were derived. A supervised Random Forest classifier was applied in Google Earth Engine to categorize land cover into forest and non-forest classes. Post-classification comparison quantified forest-cover changes over the decade. Accuracy was assessed using ground-truth GPS points and high-resolution imagery. Spatial and regression analyses were then used to identify hotspots and key drivers such as proximity to roads, elevation, and population density. The information helped to understand Land Use Land Cover change and the trend of deforestation over a 10 years interval in the study area.

Mean statistics which was binary coded was then employed to study the cause and effect of deforestation in the study area and were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). The cut off mark 3.00 represented the mean score used in determining the major causes of deforestation in the study area formatted as Strongly Agree = 5, Agree = 4, Undecided = 3, Disagree = 2, and Strongly Disagree = 1. The effect of deforestation was formatted as Very True (VT) = 5, Partially True (PT) = 4, Uncertain (U) = 3, False (F) = 2, and Very False (VF) = 1 to determine how true the statements on the effect of deforestation are in the study area. Responses were first coded

numerically and entered into the software. Frequencies and percentages were computed for each response category. Weighted mean scores (X) were then calculated by multiplying each frequency by its corresponding Likert value, summing the products, and dividing by the total number of responses. The computed means were used to rank and interpret respondents' opinions, where higher mean values indicated stronger agreement on the identified effects of deforestation in the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NATURE AND TREND OF DEFORESTATION FROM 2013 – 2023 IN OPI, NSUKKA

The study revealed that the land use/ land cover in 2013 include: built up areas, dense vegetation, exposed surfaces, and light vegetation respectively (see Figure 2 and Table 1).

Figure 2: Imagery showing land use land cover of the area of study for 2013

Source: Produced by Authors from Google Earth Data

In 2013, there was a considerable amount of deforestation taking place in the study area. Built up areas had the highest anthropogenic land use with 19%. Light vegetation which is a combination of natural grass lands, savannah, and agricultural activities had the highest score of vegetated land cover over the study area. With 42%, it accounted for almost half of the

entire land area coverage in the study area. Dense vegetation which also means areas having thick vegetation had 38% in the LULC change detection. These are undisturbed areas by deforestation and can be seen to scattered across the environs of Opi. The least land cover identified on the map in fig 2 is exposed surface with 2% (see Table 1).

Table 1: Analysis of land use land cover of the study area for 2013

Class	Sum of Area Sq/km	Percentage
Built Up Area	6.5781	19%
Dense Vegetation	12.9942	38%
Exposed Surfaces	0.5229	2%
Light Vegetation	14.3811	42%
Grand Total	34.4763	100%

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2023

In 2023, built up area had area had the highest percentage of LULC with 34%. Dense vegetation LULC reduced by 31% during the

space of ten years. Light vegetation had 30% LULC change while exposed surface is least with 5% LULC (see Table 2).

Figure 3: Imagery showing land use land cover of the area of study for 2023

Source: Produced by Authors from Google Earth Data

Table 2: Analysis of land use land cover of the study area for 2023

Class	Sum of Area Sq/km	Percentage
Built up Area	11.845	34%
Dense Vegetation	10.8006	31%
Exposed Surfaces	1.6209	5%
Light Vegetation	10.2098	30%
Grand Total	34.4763	100%

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2023

Figure 3 shows that dense vegetation reduced from 2013 (38%) to 2023 (31%) by 18.42%. Accordingly, dense vegetation is concentrated more towards the Nsukka area than it is towards Ede hill. Built up area had the highest LULC change in 2023 with 34% which is an increase from the 19% recorded in 2013. This indicates that built up areas over the study area increased within the space of 10 years by 79%. Additionally, these built-up areas are identified more towards the Nsukka urban area and spread across a wide expanse of land. Light vegetation reduced from 42% in 2013 to 30% in 2023, indicating a 29% change within the space of 10 years. The light vegetated areas are concentrated more towards the Ede hill axis.

Exposed surface increased from 2% in 2013 to 5% in 2023. This shows that the area covered by bare ground have increased within 10 years by 150%, indicating increase in development activities and deforestation.

The significant loss on vegetation using change detection analysis corresponds with the study by Onah et al., 2024 on urbanization and deforestation impacts on geomorphology and land use patterns in Enugu state and also Odoh et al., 2024 in their study “Temporal Analysis of Land Use, Land Cover, and Slope Variation in Rivers State, Nigeria: A Study from 2017 to 2023” (see the summary of LULC change in Table 3 and Figure 4).

Table 3: Summary of land use land cover change from 2013 – 2023 in the study area

LULC Type	2013		2023		LULC Changes from 2013 – 2023	
	Area (km ²)	Area (%)	Area (km ²)	Area (%)	Area Δ(km ²)	Area Δ(%)
Built Up Area	6.5781	19%	11.845	34%	5.2669	79%
Dense Vegetation	12.9942	38%	10.8006	31%	-2.1936	-18.4%
Exposed Surfaces	0.5229	2%	1.6209	5%	1.1061	150%
Light Vegetation	14.3811	42%	10.2098	30%	-4.1713	-29%
Grand Total	34.4763	100%	34.4763	100%	LULC changes from 2013 – 2023	

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2023

Figure 4: Land Use Land Cover distribution from 2013-2023

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2023

CAUSES OF DEFORESTATION

The study revealed that construction of transportation infrastructure (C1) has a mean score $X= 4.53$ making it a major cause of deforestation in Opi. Building of houses (C4) also has a high mean score of $X= 4.34$ which also makes it a major driver of deforestation. Government establishments (C3) have also contributed greatly over the last decade to deforestation in the study area. It has a mean

score of 4.33. Agricultural expansion (C5) has a mean score of $X= 4.25$. This cause stems from the conversion of dense vegetated areas to light vegetation areas for agricultural purposes. Bush burning (C6) is regarded as another major cause of deforestation in the study area and has become a common practice among locals residing at Opi. Logging activities by timber industries (C2) was also seen as a major contributor to deforestation with a mean score of 3.89 (See Table 4).

Table 4: Factors that cause deforestation in the study area

CODE	SA (%) 5	A (%) 4	U (%) 3	D (%) 2	SD (%) 1	Total (%) 15	Mean X 3
C1	80 (53) 400	70 (47) 280	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	150(100) 680	4.53
C2	20 (13) 100	100 (67) 400	24 (16) 72	6(4) 12	0 (0) 0	150(100) 584	3.89
C3	90 (60) 450	40 (27) 160	0 (0) 0	20 (13) 40	0 (0) 0	150(100) 650	4.33
C4	106 (71) 560	33 (22) 132	0 (0) 0	8 (5) 16	4 (2) 4	150(100) 651	4.34
C5	77 (51) 385	51 (34) 204	12 (8) 36	3 (2) 6	7 (4) 7	150(100) 638	4.25
C6	90 (60) 450	20 (13) 80	10 (7) 30	11 (7) 22	19(13) 19	150(100) 601	4.01

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2023

The study revealed that the major drivers of deforestation in the study area are anthropogenic. Infrastructural development activities are the leading contributor in this case as construction of roads, houses and shops have led to increased cutting of trees without replacement. This aligns with the findings by Mba, 2018 in his study “Assessment of Environmental Impact of Deforestation in Enugu”. This is followed by agricultural activities such as bush burning, and farm land expansion which has been observed in the study area. This is also evident in the work of Nzeh & Eboh 2020, where bush burning contributed significantly to deforestation in their study area, Enugu state. It has also been observed that small scale farming is widely practiced in the study area which may see deforestation continue to thrive if measures are not put in place soon. Finally, deforestation is promoted by commercial and domestic needs. This is carried out by timber industries in the

study area and the produce is sold as fuel wood or used to make furniture.

EFFECTS OF DEFORESTATION IN THE AREA

With mean scores of X= 5.00, loss of tree species (E4) as a result of deforestation, and erosion (E7) were seen as the leading effect the community suffers due to the practice of deforestation. Other effects of deforestation include; Increase in run- off (E6) with a mean score of X= 4.97. It was recorded that majority of the respondents have encountered run-off as a result of deforestation in the study area. Respondents also agreed that deforestation have led to an increase in temperature (E1) with a mean of X= 4.60. Deforestation also has an impact on the cultural heritages (E5) of the people in the study area with a mean score of X= 4.40. Air pollution (E2 X= 3.53), and water pollution (E3, X= 3.56) are also major effect of deforestation in the study area (see Table 5).

Table 5 Effects of deforestation in the study area

CODE	SA (%) 5	A (%) 4	U (%) 3	D (%) 2	SD (%) 1	Total (%) 15	Mean X 3
E1	120 (80) 600	0 (0) 0	30 (20) 90	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	150(100) 690	4.60
E2	52 (35) 260	20 (13) 80	50 (33) 150	12 (8) 24	16 (11) 16	150(100) 530	3.53
E3	66 (44) 330	17 (11) 68	17 (11) 51	35 (24) 70	15 (10) 15	150(100) 534	3.56
E4	150(100) 750	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	150(100) 750	5.00
E5	80 (53) 400	50 (34) 200	20 (13) 60	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	150(100) 660	4.40
E6	142 (95) 714	8 (5) 32	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	150(100) 746	4.97
E7	150 (100) 750	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	0 (0) 0	150(100) 750	5.00

Source: Author, 2023

As seen in Table 5, the environment has experienced the most negative impact due to deforestation. From climate change, which is manifested in the form of rising temperatures, to erosion and landscape degradation, water and air pollution, loss of tree species, and increased run-off, the environmental impact of deforestation in the study area is a serious cause for concern, particularly because of its direct alteration of the ecosystem. The finding that loss of tree species (E4, X = 5.00) and erosion (E7, X = 5.00) are the leading effects of deforestation in Opi aligns with Mba (2018) citing that the disappearance of native tree species and increased soil erosion are the most severe ecological outcomes of deforestation in the South East region. Similarly, Okorafor et al., (2017), in his review of “Soil Erosion in Southeastern Nigeria”, confirmed that vegetation removal accelerates surface runoff, resulting in gully erosion and topsoil loss in Enugu State. The observed increase in runoff (E6, X = 4.97) also supports Odoh, Nwokeabia, and Igwebudu (2024) in their study on “Urbanization and Deforestation Impacts on Geomorphology and Land Use Patterns in Enugu State” which revealed that deforestation caused by urban expansion enhances runoff and alters drainage systems in the state. The study also showed cultural heritage sites such as shrines, have been affected. A group discussion further revealed that during deforestation, dust particles being released in the atmosphere, often causes respiratory problems, including severe coughing and shortness of breath especially for asthmatic patients.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the environmental impact of deforestation in Opi, Nsukka, Enugu State, Nigeria. The findings clearly demonstrated that deforestation in the area has produced profound environmental consequences that extend beyond vegetation loss. The continuous removal of forest cover has disrupted the local climate, contributing to rising temperatures and increased surface runoff, which in turn intensify soil erosion and landscape degradation. These changes reflect a direct alteration of the ecosystem’s natural balance. Furthermore, deforestation has led to the extinction of several tree species and contamination of surface water sources due to sediment deposition and pollutant transport. Deforestation in Opi is primarily anthropogenic, driven by infrastructural expansion, agricultural encroachment, bush burning, and logging indicating the need for urgent and sustainable environmental management measures.

The study recommended that local authorities and community stakeholders adopt afforestation programmes, enforce land-use regulations, and promote environmental education and alternative livelihood options to reduce pressure on forest resources. Strengthening institutional and community-based forest management systems will be essential in mitigating the adverse impacts and restoring environmental integrity in Opi and its environs.

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